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Instructional Supervision among Headteachers of Public Junior High Schools at Atwima Kwanwoma District in the Ashanti Region.

By

Aboagye Kwadwo Samuel^{1*}

Department of Educational Leadership, Akenten Appiah-Menka University of Skills Training and Entrepreneurial Development, Kumasi, Ghana^{1*}

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Abstract:- The study looked into the effectiveness of instructional supervision among headteachers in public junior high schools in the Atwima Kwanwoma District of the Ashanti Region. The study's goals were to identify headteacher instructional supervision techniques and evaluate the effectiveness of headteacher instructional supervision in public junior high schools in the Atwima Kwanwoma District. The descriptive survey design was used, with a quantitative approach. The intended audience included all headteachers and helpers of basic public schools in the Atwima Kwanwoma District. The accessible population included 75 headteachers and assistants from the district's public junior high schools. Purposive sampling, a type of census, was employed to pick all the headteachers and helpers of the public junior high schools. Data were collected using a questionnaire with closed-ended questions. Cronbach's alpha was 0.82 according to the reliability test results. The acquired data was analyzed using descriptive statistics like frequencies and percentages. According to the survey, headteachers arranged teacher conferences and made regular visits to classrooms. Furthermore, headteachers provided effective instructional supervision by monitoring teacher quality. The challenges of instructional supervision included teachers' lack of enthusiasm and insufficient funding. Regular in-service training for heads, as well as the presence of positive human relationships, were identified as ways to improve instructional supervision. Based on the findings and conclusions, it was advised that the Atwima Kwanwoma District Directorate of Education strengthen headteachers' use of best instructional supervision techniques in schools to improve teaching and learning.

Keywords: Supervision, Instruction, Headteachers, Public, Junior High Schools.

Introduction

Through teachers, education achieves its mission of instructing and fostering students. Teachers must be educated and a part of the learning community in order to guarantee the best possible teaching-learning environment. Building good relationships with students, parents, and colleagues is one of the many instructional strategies that instructors acquire, develop, and become more adept at using (Wiles and Lovell, 2011).

In order to sustain successful education and give teachers enough resources, supervision of instruction is made to accommodate developmental demands. Caring and increasingly cooperative instruction between teachers as maturing persons is the foundation of good supervision (Frazer, 2001).

According to Glickman (2001), performance needs to be continuously examined and monitored in order to be up to date with advancements and changes. These days, supervision seems to be intermittent and frequently acts as a token exercise that falls short of the goals for which it was designed (Glickman, 2001). Thus, instructional supervision is viewed as a control mechanism whose job it is to rectify the actions of both people and groups in order to guarantee that their performance is in line with the plan. Although plans must be developed, they may not always be carried out unless activities are tracked and deviations from the plans are recognized and fixed as soon as they are noticed (Glickman, 2001).

Frazer (2001) asserts that instructional monitoring is necessary since many teachers, particularly student teachers, recently qualified teachers, and teachers with inadequate training, may not have acquired the necessary skills for effective instruction. According to Beach and Reinhartz (1989), the degree to which the instructor completes the instructional tasks satisfactorily is what matters to the instructional supervisor. To guarantee that learning continues, the instructional supervisor should be able to lead the staff in completing duties. Furthermore, the instructional supervisor should understand what makes instruction and teaching effective. Additionally, the supervisor

should be able to recognize when such effective teaching behaviours are lacking.

According to Glickman (2001), instructional supervision is the set of activities that give teachers the tools they need to better instruct students, build stronger bonds with one another, and accomplish organizational and personal objectives. Since teachers aim to enhance students' behaviour, performance, and learning capacity and supervisors want to improve teachers' behaviour, attitudes, and performance, instructional supervision is a reciprocal activity that promotes effective teaching (Glickman, Gordon & Ross-Gordon, 2001). Sergiovanni and Starrat (2015) highlighted that instructional supervision gives teachers the chance to grow in their ability to support students' academic achievement. Continuously observing the teaching process and offering advisory services while building a two-way dialogue in a cooperative partnership to raise students' academic achievement is known as instructional supervision. Instructional supervision is also a formative process that provides an opportunity to develop their capacities towards contributing to students' academic success.

According to Beach and Reinhartz (1989), supervision is a complex process that centres on education and gives teachers knowledge to help them become better teachers. One way to make sure that all of the resources offered and all of the interventions made in the teaching and learning process contribute to the achievement of the intended goals and outcomes is through effective supervision. It is crucial to remember that, despite some progress, supervision in Ghana still needs a lot of work because it doesn't seem to have gotten the full attention it needs to be effective in public schools (Cole, 2004).

A key component of administration is supervision, and any leadership role aimed at enhancing school education is seen as supervisory. Good supervision guarantees that teachers follow the curriculum and that students are sufficiently involved to get the full benefits of what is taught in the classroom.

At light of this, the study examined the efficacy of headteachers' instructional supervision at junior high

schools located in the Ashanti Region's Atwima Kwanwoma District.

Statement of The Problem

Schools rely heavily on supervision to ensure their survival. Unfortunately, basic school principals do not appear to be making appropriate use of this crucial instrument. Headteachers appear to be preoccupied with administrative tasks such as assigning assignments, attending meetings, producing reports, and so on, rather than monitoring classroom teaching. The researcher's observations suggest that teachers receive little or no monitoring in the classroom.

According to the literature search, supervision in schools is less successful. According to Antwi and Badu (2007), the quality of instruction has suffered as a result of less frequent supervision. Among the queries that come up is "What kind of supervision is done in basic schools? Is basic school supervision effective? These are the main focus of the study, which aims to find out how well headteachers in public junior high schools in the Ashanti Region's Atwima Kwanwoma District are supervised in their teaching. Its goals were to

1. determining the instructional supervision mostly used by headteachers of public Junior High schools at the Atwima Kwanwoma District in the Ashanti Region, and
2. assessing the effectiveness of headteachers' instructional supervision in public Junior High schools at Atwima Kwanwoma District in the Ashanti Region.

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What instructional supervision do headteachers of public Junior High schools at Atwima Kwanwoma District in the Ashanti Region mostly use?
2. What is the effectiveness of headteachers' instructional supervision in public Junior High schools at Atwima Kwanwoma District in the Ashanti Region?

Significantly, the study would advance supervision knowledge because the findings and recommendations would enhance basic school heads' supervision. It would highlight shortcomings in basic school headmaster monitoring so that present supervision could address them. The study's findings would assist education policymakers in creating workable regulations for efficient oversight. Because the results would serve as a foundation for more research in other areas of supervision, the study would benefit academics who might carry out comparable studies in the future. It would contribute to the body of knowledge on instructional supervision.

Literature Review Introduction

The literature covered the concept of supervision, types of supervision, qualities of a supervisor, skills of supervisors, effectiveness of school supervision, and factors for effective school supervision.

The Concept of Supervision

Cole (2004) defines supervision as the service rendered to enhance instruction and learning. Cole also claimed that supervision in schools today is not the same as it was a few years ago. Instead of writing unfavourable reports about instructors, supervision is now a collaborative endeavour or service.

The problem of school supervision has gained attention as a result of efforts to establish a direct link between teacher effectiveness and efficient supervision. According to Segun (2004), the significance of school supervision in contemporary educational systems demands a lot of attention because many people are now more aware than in the past of the fundamentals of education. Supervision is one of the administrative tools that individuals and groups of people use in the day-to-day administration of their work or organizations (Nyarko, 2009). Because of Bessong and Ojong's (2009) study, people are very interested in how the educational system runs on a daily basis.

According to Hismanoglu and Hismanoglu (2010), there are some differences in orientations, perceptions, comprehension, and familiarity with aspects of the framework as well as analysis of its content, making it difficult to agree on a specific definition of the term "educational supervision" (p. 18).

According to Neagley and Evans (2008), instructional supervision is the part of school management that focuses mostly on ensuring that the educational process's carefully chosen instructional expectations are met. According to Oghuvbu (2001), supervision of instruction entails helping people implement the curriculum and ensuring that it is being implemented positively.

These require good supervision while choosing the curriculum's structure and content, choosing school organization patterns, and choosing resources that support instructors' and students' educational development (Bessong & Ojong, 2009). According to Adesina (2001), one of the main goals of educational supervision is to ensure that each teacher fulfils their assigned responsibilities and to increase their effectiveness so they can contribute as much as possible to achieving the school's objectives (Bessong & Ojong, 2009).

According to Alemayehu (2008), supervision in the majority of schools worldwide has been centered on teacher inspection and control from the days of neo scientific administration. Performance will be much enhanced by supervision when it is conducted in a way that demonstrates growth and direction rather than criticism and judgment (Wilkinson, 2010). This demonstrates that teacher attitudes toward supervision

are critical to improving the teaching-learning process. If teachers do not see monitoring as a means of fostering professional development and student learning, the supervisory practice will not have the intended impact.

Types of Supervision

There are two primary forms of supervision found in the educational system: Internal or school-based supervision and External supervision. According to Glickman et al. (2010), internal supervision refers to the internal actions that head teachers and teachers do within the school to guarantee that school goals are met.

Glickman et al. (2010) discussed coercive supervision once more, in which the principal pays teachers a visit for the purpose of observation. One facet of internal supervision is this. Following the lesson's observation, the principal and the instructor have a meeting where the teacher receives praise for the parts of his lesson that align with what the principal "knows" constitutes effective instruction. He is then made aware of his mistakes, both in commission and omission. Once more, Glickman et al. discussed laissez-faire supervision, which is when teachers are free to act as they like with minimal guidance and forceful oversight. This entails a scenario in which a teacher is watched in action and then shown his mistakes.

On the other hand, Badu and Antwi (2007) believed that internal monitoring addressed all of the actions taken by principals and teachers in schools to improve instruction and learning. The various forms of supervision that are available and how they aid in reaching educational goals are of interest to educational researchers and educationists. Accordingly, Neagley and Evans (2008) assert that internal supervision is defined as supervision carried out by the heads of the various institutions.

The type of monitoring that takes place within the actual school is known as internal or school-based supervision. This monitoring involves head teachers, teachers, and students' leaders. The teacher's responsibilities as the primary contact supervisor include monitoring student attention during instruction, evaluating the learning process by assigning and marking exercises and other activities, and ensuring that any necessary adjustments are done. This metric improves academic performance to a great degree. The teacher must also identify the process bottlenecks and discuss them with the head teacher and the external supervisor in order to find solutions that will improve teaching and learning. The head teacher is also responsible for making sure that the school has enough teaching and learning opportunities. As the primary school supervisor, it is required of him or her to provide professional direction and counsel to the teachers and to arrange for their in-service training and on-the-job training.

Internal supervision is defined by Adentwi (2001) as supervision conducted by a member of the team in charge of organizing and carrying out the program under supervision or evaluation. According to the Circuit

Supervisors' Handbook (Ghana Education Service, 2002), external supervision is carried out by officers or people who are not connected to the particular institution. Their goal is to provide teachers with knowledgeable guidance and advice in order to support the duties and responsibilities of the internal supervisor or supervisors. The role of external supervisors in school management is quite important. The district inspectorate teams and circuit supervisors from the district education office are prominent among them. External supervision is therefore the supervision that comes from outside, notably from the district office, regional or national office. Therefore, external supervision refers to supervision that originates from outside, particularly from the national, regional, or district office. Brief visits, familiarization visits, assessment for promotion visits, special visits, follow-up visits, and intense or comprehensive visits are among the several forms of external supervision (Neagley & Evans, 2008).

During a brief visit, the officer concentrates on one or two areas of the school. For instance, a visit to verify the collection of levies or the instructors' punctuality. During a familiarization visit, a recently hired circuit officer goes to schools in the circuit to meet staff, students, and members of the local community. For the same reason, a supervisor might also pay a visit to a recently opened school. A follow-up visit is also conducted to determine the extent to which the suggestions in an earlier report have been put into practice (Neagley & Evans, 2008).

Assessment for promotion visit: In order to examine the work of a teacher who is due for promotion, a group of supervisors may be asked to visit the school. A special visit refers to a circumstance in which a supervisor might be called to visit a school in order to look into allegations of misconduct or charges made against a headmaster, instructor, or students. According to Neagley and Evans (2008), this kind of visit is unique and occasionally referred to as an investigative visit.

Intensive or comprehensive visit is also conducted by a group of officials, particularly circuit supervisors from the district education office, who evaluate the entire curriculum to make sure that teaching and learning are conducted effectively in the classroom. Depending on the number of officers involved, these visits, which are marked by clinical support, could take three days (Neagley & Evans, 2008).

Qualities of a Supervisor

High-level educational leadership professionals are needed to implement monitoring. To effectively perform their jobs, supervisors need to possess supervisory skills and abilities. According to Cojocar (2010), supervisors should possess the following attributes. In order to prevent errors, supervisors should communicate instructions in a clear and concise manner. Supervisors must pay close attention to what the teachers have to say as well. People respond negatively to something they

believe to be unjust. Teachers should therefore be treated fairly. Coordinating the work at the offices and schools for the director and teachers is the responsibility of the supervisors.

Supervisors should constantly be one step ahead of their subordinates, as it is part of their role to train others. Unless they have wilfully ignored their supervisors' directions, teachers should always take responsibility for their mistakes. Supervisors must always be prepared to take on the next duty if they want schools to succeed. Even if you disagree with change, be prepared to handle it effectively when it occurs. At all times, the supervisors should be polite.

Supervisors should never reprimand a teacher in front of other teachers; instead, they should do so in a firm but kind manner. Nobody should be embarrassed since everyone makes errors. It is not a good idea to yell at instructors since it will make them angry and resentful. Supervisors should not be scared to commend their teachers for a job well done, and they should accomplish more with a smile than with hostility. In addition to their employers, who provide their salaries, the supervisors are loyal to the teachers, who bear the responsibility for their performance. It takes a lot of tact to strike this delicate balance.

Supervisors should inspire respect so, discretion in their private lives is essential, nor can they tell teachers of lateness if the supervisors are always late themselves.

According to Cojocar (2010), having the aforementioned traits will enable supervisors to effectively oversee, which will enhance instruction and learning in classrooms and raise educational standards. Furthermore, according to Cojocar, a modern supervisor needs to possess the character traits of an effective educator. He or she must possess intelligence, a thorough understanding of society's educational system, a positive disposition, and excellent interpersonal skills.

The supervisor needs to show that they have a realistic understanding of the team concept when it comes to democratic oversight. Furthermore, the supervisor's own views must sometimes yield to the team's judgment. The supervisor must be able and strong enough to stand by his beliefs. The results of educational research should always serve as a guide for a good supervisor, who should also have ample opportunity for constructive criticism during both individual and group conferences.

Furthermore, it is impossible for the supervisor to be an authority in every area they oversee. Although the supervisor may be an expert in some fields, they must have a broad perspective on the entire curriculum. In summary, Cojocar (2010) suggests that the modern supervisor needs to be able to supervise, have a strong background in psychology and education, and be knowledgeable about the democratic group process.

Skills of Supervisors

Chance and Chance (2002) define educational leadership as the process of involving and guiding the abilities and efforts of students, faculty, and other stakeholders in order to achieve common educational objectives. To accomplish the tasks assigned to them, supervisors who are seen as leaders in education need to possess extraordinary skills.

Ricketts (2003) and Pajebo (2009) Sort the skills needed by supervisors into three groups: conceptual, human, and technical (know-how). Technical skills, according to Pajebo, include knowledge of and proficiency with methodology, process, processes, and techniques. He continues by saying that knowledge of finance, accounting, purchasing, and maintenance are examples of non-instructional skills. Ricketts also considers technical skills to be "doing". Enhancing public speaking, time management, communication, prepared speaking, group dynamics, goal setting and activity planning, money management, running productive meetings, and organizational abilities are among a supervisor's technical competencies.

According to Pajebo (2009), the capacity to interact with people in both one-on-one and group settings is known as human relations competency. Human relations involve a high level of self-awareness, acceptance, respect, sensitivity, and consideration for others. Adult motivation, attitude development, group dynamics, human needs, conflict resolution, and human resource development are examples of human relations skills that a supervisor should possess.

As examples of a supervisor's human relations skills, Ricketts (2003) listed the following: honesty, the ability to work hard, cooperativeness, attentive listening, strong self-concept, enjoyment of working with people, sensitivity and positive attitude, interpersonal communication, the ability to get along with others, the variety of attitudes and values people have, motives that others may have, good self-concept, and self-esteem. According to Ricketts (2003), conceptual (thinking) skills refer to a supervisor's capacity to see the institution and all of its programs as one. This speaks to how well the pieces are mapped. Good imagination, education, integrating concepts and ideas into a feasible solution, problem-solving abilities, creativity, logical thinking, sound decision-making abilities, anticipating issues, independent thought, foreseeing change, open-mindedness, and welcoming new opportunities are some of the conceptual skills he lists. The inference is that in order to effectively navigate the challenges that his job brings, the supervisor, as a leader, should possess technical, conceptual, and interpersonal skills.

Effectiveness of School Supervision

The ability to create an effect is what is meant by effectiveness. Effectiveness in management is defined as completing tasks correctly. Additionally, the degree to which goals are achieved, and particular issues are fixed serves as a gauge of efficacy. While efficiency is defined as "doing the thing right," effectiveness is defined as

"doing the right thing" and is evaluated independently of costs (Drucker, 2006). In schools, school leaders must do the right thing in order to achieve educational goals.

Effective supervision, according to Gordon (2004), is provided by qualified professionals who possess the technical know-how, interpersonal skills, and expertise necessary to give teaching staff the necessary and suitable guidance and assistance. Effective supervision should promote teacher development and learning, claims Duke (1993). Effective supervision has been described in a variety of ways by some researchers. Jones (1993) thought that in order to examine what really happens in the classroom, effective monitoring was necessary. Brennen (2008) agreed, saying that a great supervisor who has both technical and people abilities will be beneficial in enhancing instruction. In actuality, not every supervisor can handle every supervisory responsibility.

Effective supervision gives teachers confidence in their abilities to isolate, analyse, and create problem-solving approaches. It aids in determining if a teacher ought to be promoted, transferred, detained, or sacked. It aids in assessing the school's most pressing needs, determining the efficacy of classroom management by the teacher, and providing a guide for staff development (Mgbadille, 1996).

Assessing the Caliber of instructors and schools is one of the most crucial roles of any system of school supervision, according to UNESCO (2007). This effective supervision is likely to improve quality. Effective supervision is part of a larger quality monitoring and improvement system that incorporates other tools like exams and achievement tests, as well as self-assessment activities by schools and teachers.

Effective school supervision encourages teaching and learning in schools. Lack of supervision may result in inadequate teacher training, a bad attitude toward school, and an uncondusive school climate. These are common problems which affect classroom engagement, school discipline, and teacher effectiveness (Oghuvbu 2013). These prevalent school disciplinary issues are the result of insufficient supervision, which is caused by insufficient funding and skilled staff in the Ministry of Education's inspection division. Teachers' cooperation is lacking, and their working conditions are bad (Oghuvbu, 2013). Effective school supervision helps principals and teachers perform better in administrative and instructional roles (Oghuvbu, 2013).

An organizational behaviour system called supervision works in tandem with the teaching behaviour system to enhance the learning environment for students (Onoyase, 2011). Nonetheless, monitoring needs to be done within the educational system, and every system has a variety of factors that can interfere with the system's ability to operate as a whole. Nonetheless, there are issues with instructional monitoring in the classroom. These difficulties manifest as issues and are talked about:

When there aren't enough motivating factors in their work, supervisors may get dissatisfied. A number of individuals who are not directly involved in a particular method or activity may receive more money and awards than those who actually completed the assignment because of the high level of corruption in the nation (Onoyase, 2011). The way that instructional supervision is conducted in secondary schools may occasionally be impacted by this particular behaviour.

Economic in nature, the problem of limited resources aims to decrease waste by rationalizing spending. On the other hand, without the required funding, it would be challenging to establish effective instructional supervision (Onoyase, 2011). To have things organized before monitoring, school administrators and instructional supervisors would require specific resources; the supervisory process would be impacted if these resources were unavailable.

When planning does not outline the extent of duties and outcomes that instructional supervision is supposed to achieve in a school, administrative shortcomings become apparent (Eya & Leonard, 2012). As a result, the supervisee should be informed in detail about the scheduled visits and the agreement established between the supervisee and the supervisor regarding the procedures and goals. To put it another way, if instructional supervision is to accomplish its goals, school administrators and the instructional supervisor must agree (Eya & Leonard, 2012).

In this sense, both instructional supervisors and school administrators are judged culpable. Instructional supervision in secondary schools would not benefit from unholy cooperation between the supervisor and the school administration over cash intended to purchase supplies for the system. Instructional supervisors are in the best position to spot financial misappropriation in schools, but if they are not well compensated, the issue will persist and have an impact on the criteria that the educational system should meet (Eya & Leonard, 2012).

Government rules pertaining to instructional supervision typically undergo constant modification as a result of numerous changes in government. The policies and programs implemented by the preceding administration are frequently discontinued by the succeeding administration in emerging nations like Ghana. This one action typically has an impact on how well instruction is supervised in schools. Put another way, contradictory policies regarding the kind of individuals who should be involved and how education should be observed in schools would negatively impact and present a significant challenge to instructional supervision, particularly in secondary schools (Anderson, 2008).

Factors for Effective School Supervision

According to Nolan and Francis (1992), supervision offers a way for supervisors and teachers to learn more about the teaching-learning process by working together with other experts. Baffour-Awuah claims that the term

"supervision" was originally used to refer to inspection, which implies that school inspectors had direct authority over teachers. According to Marzano, Frontier, and Livingston (2011), a supportive environment, staff orientation, training, acknowledging good work, offering constructive criticism, providing logistics, and teamwork all affect efficient and successful school supervision.

A conducive learning environment is one that permits a free flow of ideas and is free from both emotional and physical intimidation. Since teachers and students are the main advocates of the educational process, their freedom of movement, safety, and respect ought to be equally protected in the emotional and physical surroundings in which they find themselves. Tension and emotional stress should be eliminated from the atmosphere. There should be incentives for work in the atmosphere (Mushtaq & Khan, 2012).

Orientation is a personnel activity that introduces new hires to the company and their tasks. The workforce is unfamiliar with the job, the supervision pattern, or who to see to complete the assignment (Hake, 1998). Therefore, in order to make new supervisors effective, they need to be integrated into the work system. Clear guidelines must be established on the Caliber and volume of their labour. They ought to be given a clear understanding of what is expected of them. To enable them to meet standards sooner, new supervisors must receive the required orientation. They should have a timetable, so they know where to find the knowledge and resources they need to do their jobs well (Hijazi & Naqvi, 2006).

It is claimed that training is a methodical process for changing employees' behaviour in a way that advances organizational objectives. Training is connected to one's current job competencies. It has a modern focus and assists staff in developing the particular competencies required for success. Ivancevich (1998). Given this, it is essential to acquire and apply knowledge for efficient supervision. In order to improve supervisors' expertise, conferences, workshops, and in-service training must be conducted in a way that provides them with up-to-date supervision tools. According to Tanner and Tanner (1987), the supervisor's quality should be seen as crucial for supervision to accomplish its goals.

Effective supervision requires acknowledging good work. A supervisor's guidance is ineffective when there is a failure to acknowledge the excellent work that teachers do. It is important to acknowledge good effort. This suggests that any good job must be acknowledged right away and shared with others, as this will encourage others to do the same. Performance is improved by merit-based incentives, promotion recommendations, etc. (Noble & Sawyer, 2006).

Teachers greatly benefit from work criticism. Supervisors must provide constructive criticism for subordinates' subpar work. The impacted staff members should receive personal relationships and advice. It is important

to note that these kinds of critiques ought to be made in private and with objectivity (Noble & Sawyer, 2006).

Subordinates should be given the chance to demonstrate their value and to aim higher by their supervisors. Therefore, they ought to be permitted to use initiative when carrying out their duties and making decisions. They will be inspired to put in considerably more effort as a result (Noble & Sawyer, 2006).

The foundation upon which supervision is built is logistics. Logistics and work supplies must be readily available since they inspire confidence in managers and employees. Because motivation is likely to decline, a lack of logistics might significantly impede supervisors' work or slow down the pace of work. According to Halpin (1956), monitoring can be carried out successfully if the necessary logistics are in place.

For every firm to succeed, team building is crucial. In order to unite all partners as a team, supervisors and employees must work together. The group needs to develop a shared vision or goal, believe in it, and collaborate as a team (Noble & Sawyer, 2006).

Methodology

For this research, a descriptive survey design was employed. The researcher was able to choose a sample from a variety of workplaces that reflected the larger community thanks to the design (White, 2005).

Every headmaster and assistant in the district's 37 public junior high schools was specifically selected for the study through a sort of census from a target population of 75 (Foley, 2018).

A questionnaire was used to gather data, and Likert-type scale items were used for instrumentation. There were three parts to the questionnaire. The respondents' demographic data was included in Section A. While Section C asked respondents to rate the efficacy of heads' instructional supervision, Section B described the type of supervision that was offered. The instrument was pre-tested and verified in compliance with Riemenschneider, Leonard, and Manly (2019) and Babbie and Mounton (2016). The instrument's Cronbach alpha of 0.81 indicated that it was suitable for the study.

The data collection process was conducted while abiding by all confidentiality, anonymity, and voluntariness requirements after building rapport with the respondents at the schools. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages were then used to analyse the data in order to address the study's goals.

Results and Discussions

Respondents' Demographic Characteristics

The study looked at the demographics of the participants, including their age, gender, greatest level of education, and prior teaching experience. In order for the researcher to determine the type of respondents he utilized in the study, these were necessary. The gender

of the study participants is the subject of the first section of the analysis. This can be found in Table 4.1.

Table 1: Gender of Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Male	36	48
Female	39	52
Total	75	100

Source: Field Data, 2024

According to Table 1, 52% of respondents were female and 48% of respondents were male. The findings suggest that a greater proportion of women than men took part in the research.

Highest Level of Education

Analysis was also done on the respondents' highest level of schooling. This was done in order to determine the respondents' level of education. Details are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Highest Level of Educational

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor's Degree	49	65
Master's Degree	26	35
Total	75	100

Source: Field Data, 2024

According to Table 2, 35% of respondents held a master's degree, whereas 65% of respondents held a bachelor's degree. According to the findings, the majority of respondents have bachelor's degrees, indicating that they possess the necessary training and expertise to take part in the study.

Table 4: Headteachers' Instructional Supervision Provided

Statement	Strongly Agree		Agree		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Regularly visits classroom	28	37	27	36	20	27	-	-	75	100
Mutually plan lesson observation with teachers	37	49	23	31	10	13	5	7	75	100
Provides immediate feedback on supervision to teachers	32	43	24	32	12	16	7	9	75	100
Provides resource materials to improve teaching	31	41	25	33	14	19	5	7	75	100
Substitutes teaching on occasions	34	45	23	31	18	24	-	-	75	100
Establishes high instructional goals to be achieved by teachers	31	41	30	40	14	19	-	-	75	100
Provides effective leadership in classroom	27	36	30	40	15	20	3	4	75	100

Source: Field Data, 2024

Duration of Service

We also looked at the respondents' length of service. Finding out how long respondents had been teaching was the goal of this survey. The results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Number of Years in the Teaching Profession

Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
1-5 years	11	15
6-10 years	24	32
11-15 years	19	25
16 years and above	21	28
Total	75	100

Source: Field Data, 2024

15% of respondents had been teaching for one to five years, 32% for six to ten years, 25% for eleven to fifteen years, and 28% for sixteen years or more, according to Table 3. According to the findings, the majority of respondents had sufficient experience to take part in the survey because they had been teachers for six to ten years.

Data Analysis

Research Question 1: What instructional supervision do headteachers in Public Junior High schools at Atwima Kwanwoma District mostly use?

Several questions about headteachers' methods of instructional supervision were posed to the respondents. Table 4 displays the outcome.

According to Table 4, the majority of respondents (37%) strongly agreed that head teachers conducted frequent classroom visits, with 36% agreeing. More than 27% of those surveyed didn't agree. As a result, heads visit classrooms on a frequent basis. The outcome supports Asiedu-Akrofi's (1978) assertion that, among other things, supervisors conduct action research in the classroom and conduct frequent classroom visits.

Additionally, 31% of respondents agreed and 49% of respondents strongly agreed that headteachers and teachers collaborated to prepare lesson observations. Seven percent of respondents strongly disagreed, and more than thirteen percent disagreed. The outcome indicates that headteachers' instructional supervision practice involves them planning lesson observations in tandem with teachers. The outcome complies with Blasé and Blasé's (2018) recommendation that supervisors and teachers collaborate to design lesson observations rather than supervisors showing up in the classroom unannounced and using pre-established rating items.

About 43% majority of the respondents strongly that head teachers regularly provided objective feedback about the observation of lessons, and 32% of the respondents agreed. Over 16% of the respondents disagreed while 9% of the respondents strongly disagreed. The result means that heads provide objective feedback about the observation of the lesson. The result is in tandem with Noble & Sawyer, (2006) position that the prime justification for the position of supervision in the school is to give leadership and provide feedback to the teaching and learning process.

Also, 41% majority of the respondents strongly agreed that head teachers provided resource materials to improve teaching, and 33% of the respondents agreed. Over 19% of the respondents disagreed while 7% of the respondents strongly disagreed. The result means that heads provide resource materials to improve teaching. The result agrees with Enaigbe's (2009) assertion that

there can be no effective supervision of instruction without adequate instructional materials. Materials like supervision guides and manuals have their own impact on supervision work.

Again, 45% majority of the respondents strongly agreed that head teachers substituted teaching on occasions, 31% of the respondents agreed. Over 24% of the respondents disagreed. The result means that heads substitute teaching on occasions. The result is in tandem with Neagley and Evans's (2008) assertion that supervisors substitute teaching on occasion.

About 41% of respondents strongly agreed, with 40% agreeing, that head teachers set high standards for instruction that teachers must meet. More than 19% of those surveyed didn't agree. The outcome is that head teachers set high standards for instruction that must be met by their teachers. The outcome supports the claim made by Hallinger and Murphy (2015) that supervision gives heads a means of keeping an eye on instruction. Heads utilize classroom visits to ensure that teachers are adhering to the school's educational objectives.

Once more, 36% of respondents strongly agreed and 40% of respondents felt that head teachers exercised effective leadership in the classroom. Four percent of respondents strongly disagreed, while more than twenty percent disagreed. As a result, teachers are able to effectively lead their classes. The outcome supports Wiles' (2000) assertion that supervision entails exercising effective classroom leadership.

Table 2: Barriers of parent involvement in students' academic performance

Research Question 2: What is the effectiveness of headteachers' instructional supervision in Public Junior High Schools at Atwima Kwanwoma District?

Several questions about the efficacy of heads' instructional supervision were posed to the respondents. Table 5 displays the outcome.

Table 5: Effectiveness of Instructional Supervision

Statement	Strongly Agree		Agree		Disagree		Mean	Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Increases teachers' confidence in the teaching and learning process	33	44	25	33	12	16	3.15	75 100
Supports teachers to use appropriate pedagogical skills of teachers	35	47	22	29	15	20	3.19	75 100
Encourages teachers to develop a range of teaching strategies	29	39	28	37	18	24	-	3.15 75 100
Monitors teachers' instructional performance	31	41	25	33	14	19	3.09	75 100
Checks teachers' classroom management practices	36	48	25	33	14	19	-	3.29 75 100

Monitors the quality of teaching	30	40	22	29	18	24	5	7	3.03	75	100
Assists teachers to manage their weaknesses	27	36	32	43	16	21	-		3.15	75	100
Provides adequate instructional materials	30	40	30	40	10	13	5	7	3.13	75	100
Overall Mean									3.15		

Source: Field Data, 2024

According to Table 5, 44% of respondents strongly agreed that head teachers boosted students' confidence in the process of teaching and learning. About 33% of respondents said they agreed, 16% said they disagreed, and 7% said they strongly disagreed. As a result, head teachers boost their instructors' confidence in the process of teaching and learning. The outcome confirms Brennen's (2008) claim that good supervision gave teachers more self-assurance in the teaching and learning process and the capacity to separate.

The majority of respondents (more than 47%) strongly believed that head teachers help instructors develop their instructional abilities. More than 29% of those surveyed concurred. The assertion was disputed by 20% of the responders. Just 4% of those surveyed said they strongly disagreed. The outcome indicates that instructional monitoring by headteachers helps instructors advance their pedagogical abilities. This suggests that educators can meet expectations and assist schools in achieving their objectives.

Additionally, the majority of respondents (39%) strongly agreed that head teachers pushed instructors to use a variety of instructional techniques. The assertion was accepted by more than 37% of the respondents. Of those surveyed, about 24% disagreed. As a result, head teachers support their instructors in creating a variety of instructional methodologies. The outcome supports the claim made by Blase and Roberts (2014) that good supervision motivates educators to create a variety of instructional techniques so that students can learn more effectively during class.

Additionally, 41% of respondents strongly agreed that head teachers keep an eye on teachers' performance in the classroom. Approximately one-third of them concurred with the assertion. Of them, only 7% strongly disagreed. According to the findings, heads kept an eye on instructors' performance in the classroom. This suggests that educators will carry out their duties in the classroom efficiently, which will enhance students' academic success.

It was also strongly agreed upon by 48% of respondents that head teachers reviewed classroom management procedures. Approximately 33% of those surveyed agreed, while 19% disapproved. The remark was strongly disagreed with by only 7% of them. The outcome indicates the methods used by head teachers to manage their classrooms. This will improve verify teachers' job

and increase their efficacy. The outcome supports Brennen's (2008) claim that teachers can enhance their classroom management abilities with the use of efficient monitoring.

29% of respondents agreed, and more than 40% strongly agreed that head teachers kept an eye on instructors' quality. Approximately 24% of respondents disagreed, and 7% strongly disagreed. This suggests that educators will use efficient techniques to improve students' comprehension of the lesson. As a result, head teachers keep an eye on instructors' quality for efficient supervision. The outcome supports UNESCO's (2007) claim that overseeing teacher quality is one of the primary responsibilities of the school supervisor. It is anticipated that this efficient oversight will improve quality.

On helping teachers deal with their shortcomings, the majority of responders (43%), agreed that head teachers helped teachers manage their teaching inadequacies. Of those surveyed, 36% strongly agreed. Approximately 21% of those surveyed disagreed. As a result, head teachers assist teachers in addressing their areas of instructional weakness. It follows that teachers will become more knowledgeable about teaching strategies, which will help the school achieve its objectives.

Once more, the majority of respondents (40%) strongly felt that head teachers supplied sufficient teaching resources. More than 40% of those surveyed concurred. Approximately 13% of respondents disagreed, and 7% strongly disagreed. As a result, head teachers offer sufficient teaching resources to assist instruction. Teachers will be able to deliver in a methodical way to encourage classroom efficiency thanks to this.

It may be concluded that most respondents agreed with the construct items because the mean scores of all the items were nearly 3. The respondents agreed that head teachers' instructional monitoring was successful, as indicated by the overall mean value of 3.15.

Conclusion

It was determined that heads scheduled teacher observations. Because they participated in the observations, instructors also became more dedicated, and heads were able to concentrate on their duties. Additionally, the effectiveness of the headteachers' instructional supervision was determined. This

enhanced instruction and learning to guarantee the accomplishment of the schools' overarching objectives.

According to the study, headteachers and teachers collaborated to prepare lesson observations for instructional oversight. Other elements include giving teachers prompt feedback on their monitoring, offering them resources to help them teach better, occasionally substituting teaching, and setting high standards for education that teachers must meet.

According to the study's findings, headteachers' instructional supervision was successful in boosting teachers' self-assurance in the teaching and learning process, enhancing their pedagogical abilities, motivating them to create a variety of teaching strategies, keeping an eye on their instructional performance, assessing their classroom management techniques, assessing the caliber of their instruction, helping them manage their areas of weakness, and providing them with sufficient teaching resources.

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Recommendation

Based on the study's findings, the Atwima Kwanwoma District Directorate of Education was advised to support headteachers' implementation of best instructional supervision techniques in schools in order to enhance instruction and learning.

Suggestions for Further Studies

The study looked into how well head teachers in public junior high schools in the Ashanti Region's Atwima Kwanwoma District implemented instructional supervision. In order to dispute or validate the study's conclusions, additional research could be conducted in the Ashanti Region's remaining districts, municipalities, and metro areas.

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